

Comparison of Model Order Reduction methods in Thermoacoustic Stability Analysis

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ABSTRACT

Model order reduction can play a pivotal role in reducing the cost of repeated computations of large thermoacoustic models required for comprehensive stability analysis and optimization. In this proof-of-concept study, acoustic wave propagation is modeled with a 1D network approach, while acoustic-flame interactions are modeled by a flame transfer function. Three reduction techniques are applied to the acoustic subsystem: firstly modal truncation based on preserving the acoustic eigenmodes, and then two approaches that strive to preserve the input-output transfer behavior of the acoustic subsystem, i.e., truncated balanced realization and iterative rational Krylov algorithm. After reduction, the reduced-order models (ROMs) are coupled with the flame transfer function. Results show that the coupled reduced system from modal truncation accurately captures thermoacoustic cavity modes with weak influence of the flame, but fails for cavity modes strongly

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influenced by the flame as well as for intrinsic thermoacoustic modes. On the contrary, the coupled ROMs generated with the other two methods accurately predict all types of modes. It is concluded that reduction techniques based on preserving transfer behavior are more suitable for thermoacoustic stability analysis.

NOMENCLATURE

- p' Acoustic pressure
- u' Acoustic velocity
- u'_{ref} Acoustic velocity at reference location
- \dot{q}' Unsteady heat release rate
- $(\hat{\cdot})$ Quantity in Laplace domain
- \mathbf{x} State vector in state-space model
- u Input for state-space model
- y Output for state-space model
- $\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}$ System matrix and vectors for state-space model
- \Re Real part
- \Im Imaginary part
- λ Eigenvalue
- r Order of the reduced-order model
- ω Frequency
- \mathbf{V}, \mathbf{W} Projection matrices
- \mathbf{W}_c Controllability Gramian
- \mathbf{W}_o Observability Gramian
- \mathbf{R}, \mathbf{S} Matrices from Cholesky Decomposition of $\mathbf{W}_c, \mathbf{W}_o$
- Σ Diagonal matrix with Hankel Singular Values
- \mathbf{U}, \mathbf{P} Matrices with left and right singular vectors
- G Transfer function
- s Laplace variable or Expansion point for IRKA method
- $(\cdot)_r$ Quantity for reduced order system
- $(\cdot)_{\text{MT}}$ for Modal Truncation
- $(\cdot)_{\text{TB}}$ for Truncated Balanced Realization
- $(\cdot)_{\text{Kr}}$ for Iterative Rational Krylov algorithm

1 INTRODUCTION

Modern low-emission gas turbines and aero-engines often face challenges of thermoacoustic instabilities. If the Rayleigh criterion is fulfilled, unsteady heat release driven by acoustic perturbations adds acoustic energy to the system [1]. When this addition surpasses the acoustic losses, thermoacoustic instability occurs. It is of particular interest for industry to predict the risk of thermoacoustic instabilities in the early design stage. Thus, thermoacoustic stability analysis has become a crucial step in combustor development. Linear stability analysis (LSA) is a common method to predict frequencies and growth rates of thermoacoustic modes. To perform LSA, linearized models are derived from the governing equations of the relevant physics. Linearized Navier-Stokes (LNSE), Linearized Euler or Helmholtz equations are examples of linearized governing equations that model the acoustics of a domain [2–5]. Models of acoustic wave propagation in simple acoustic elements can be connected to build a network model of a larger domain with non-trivial topology [6–8]. The flame response to acoustic velocity perturbation can be represented by a Flame Transfer Function (FTF). The flame model can be coupled with the acoustic model in a state-space framework to build a hybrid thermoacoustic setup [8–11]. Note that in such a hybrid setup, there are two subsystems that govern the flame dynamics and the acoustics separately.

For a hybrid thermoacoustic setup, uncertainties are involved in the identification of the flame dynamics, especially for turbulent flames [12]. Therefore, repeated computations on the same acoustic subsystem coupled with different realizations of the flame model is generally needed for robust LSA. Apart from linear analysis, a non-linear flame model or numerical simulation of the flame can also be coupled with the linear model of the acoustic subsystem to predict limit-cycle amplitudes in the time-domain [10, 13], where computation is repeated with every time-step using the same linear acoustic model. Such repetitive computations in frequency domain or with time-stepping can be prohibitively expensive for extended, complex acoustic domains. Thus, model order reduction (MOR) of the acoustic subsystem – referred to as the “full-order model” (FOM) in the following – can play a pivotal role in reducing the computational cost by deriving a reduced-order model (ROM) with significantly fewer degrees of freedom and approximately the same dynamics.

MOR has been applied extensively in the field of control systems, structural mechanics, and fluid dynamics [14, 15]. In this study, we consider the acoustic subsystem in the hybrid setup as an input-output system, where the input and output are heat release rate fluctuation \dot{q}' and acoustic velocity perturbation u'_{ref} at a reference location upstream of the flame, respectively. We apply three MOR methods to the acoustic subsystem, i.e., modal truncation (MT), truncated balanced realization (TBR) and iterative rational Krylov algorithm (IRKA). These methods may be categorized into two types: MT is based on a subset of selected eigenmodes of the acoustic subsystem, while both TBR and IRKA strive to preserve the transfer behavior, i.e., the input-output relation of the acoustic subsystem. To

build a reduced thermoacoustic model, the ROM of the acoustic subsystem is coupled with the flame model. It is the goal of the presented methodology that the analysis of this reduced thermoacoustic system yields approximately the same results as the full thermoacoustic system.

In the literature, MOR methods applied for thermoacoustic applications have generally been based on modal or Galerkin expansion of the acoustic system, which is a form of modal truncation. With modal truncation, one can retain those eigenmodes of the FOM that are physically relevant for thermoacoustic oscillations. The basis functions of the modal expansion can be derived analytically [16–18] or with numerical computations [19], depending on the geometrical complexity of the domain. Bethke et al. [20] and Hummel et al. [21] demonstrate model reduction by retaining a small number of physically important eigenmodes of the acoustic subsystem constructed with FEM discretization of their respective acoustic domains. However, modal truncation poses a challenge for MOR of an acoustic domain with general boundary conditions. This is addressed by Laurent et al. [22] by using a modal basis with an over-complete set of eigenmodes.

Modal truncation can be disadvantageous if \dot{q}' from the flame significantly impacts the coupled system, such that the shape or frequency of the thermoacoustic eigenmodes differ considerably from the passive acoustic modes, c.f. Sayadi et al. [23]. In this case, the feedback from \dot{q}' to u'_{ref} has a dominant role in determining the thermoacoustic modes and this feedback cannot be captured only with the eigenmodes of the acoustic subsystem. Therefore, preserving the input-output relation of the acoustic subsystem can provide better results. In a preliminary study, Meindl et al. [24] indicate that ROMs of the acoustic subsystem derived using TBR and IRKA, in comparison to modal truncation, provide better accuracy in capturing the eigenvalue of intrinsic thermoacoustic modes after coupling with the flame model. However, no detailed explanation for this observation was provided and accuracy for other thermoacoustic modes was not investigated. The current study presents the first detailed investigation on the application of MOR methods based on preserving the transfer behavior (TBR and IRKA) in thermoacoustics and compares them with modal truncation. This study shows that the reduced thermoacoustic systems derived using TBR and IRKA predict the eigenvalues and eigenmode shapes of the thermoacoustic cavity modes that differ significantly from the passive acoustic modes due to strong influence of the flame, and intrinsic modes with better accuracy than the reduced system from modal truncation.

In the next section, we give a brief description of the thermoacoustic setup considered in this study. In Section 3, the MOR methods applied in this study are explained. In Section 4, two ways of comparing the MOR methods are presented - one with respect to the relative error in the transfer function of the ROMs; the other in terms of the error in capturing thermoacoustic modes after coupling with the FTF.

2 THERMOACOUSTIC MODEL

The acoustic setup of the combustor considered in this study is modeled using the in-house network modeling tool *taX* developed at TU Munich [25]. The setup comprises simple 1D acoustic elements - ducts, area jumps and boundaries with given reflection coefficient. *taX* connects these individual 1D acoustic elements using the Riemann invariants f and g representing acoustic wave propagation in down- and upstream direction, respectively. Primitive acoustic variables p' and u' are related to f and g as:

$$\begin{aligned} p' &= \overline{\rho c}(f + g) \\ u' &= f - g \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where, ρ and c are density and speed of sound respectively, $\overline{(\cdot)}$ represent mean of the quantity.

Figure 1 shows the hybrid thermoacoustic setup where the acoustic subsystem is depicted in the dashed box. The input to the acoustic subsystem is heat release rate perturbation \hat{q}' and the output is acoustic velocity fluctuation u'_{ref} at a reference location upstream of the flame. *taX* provides a state-space formulation of this acoustic subsystem with the above mentioned input and output. The state-space representation of the spatially discretized acoustic subsystem is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\mathbf{x}} &= \mathbf{A} \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{b} \hat{q}' \\ u'_{\text{ref}} &= \mathbf{c} \mathbf{x} \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

where, $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^N$ is the state vector containing the acoustic perturbations at the discretization nodes, $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$ is the system matrix, $\mathbf{b} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times 1}$ relates the input \hat{q}' to \mathbf{x} , and $\mathbf{c} \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times N}$ relates the output u'_{ref} to \mathbf{x} . This subsystem is then coupled with a Flame Transfer Function (FTF) to build a full thermoacoustic model as shown in Fig. 1. The FTF is defined as follows :

$$\frac{\hat{q}'}{\bar{Q}} = \frac{\hat{u}'_{\text{ref}}}{\bar{u}_{\text{ref}}} \text{FTF}(s) \tag{3}$$

where, $\hat{(\cdot)}$ represent the variable in Laplace domain and \bar{Q} is the mean heat release rate of the flame. The FTF can be represented as another state-space model as applied by Meindl et al. [11].

We will be applying MOR to the acoustic subsystem only. The motivation for this has been discussed in the Introduction and is reiterated here: repeated computations on a hybrid thermoacoustic model with the same acoustic subsystem can be accelerated if an ROM of the acoustic subsystem is used. Thus, the acoustic subsystem is the full-order model (FOM) in this study and the flame model remains untouched. After reduction, the ROM is coupled with the flame model to get the reduced thermoacoustic model. In the rest of the study, following terms are used to refer to (un-)coupled systems :

- FOM or uncoupled FOM: full acoustic subsystem (with no coupling to the flame model)
- ROM or uncoupled ROM: reduced order acoustic subsystem (with no coupling to the flame model)
- coupled FOM or full thermoacoustic system: full acoustic subsystem coupled with the flame model
- coupled ROM or reduced thermoacoustic system: reduced acoustic subsystem coupled with the flame model

In a thermoacoustic system, two types of thermoacoustic modes exist: acoustic modes and intrinsic modes [26–31]. The acoustic modes of a thermoacoustic system (here, the coupled FOM) are closely related to the acoustic modes of its acoustic subsystem (the uncoupled FOM) [27]. In the rest of the study, the acoustic modes of the coupled FOM are referred as the thermoacoustic cavity modes. Figure 2 shows the eigenvalues of the coupled and uncoupled FOM. The eigenvalues of the uncoupled FOM belong to the passive acoustic eigenmodes, whereas the eigenvalues of the coupled system include intrinsic modes (one at 111 Hz) and thermoacoustic cavity modes. The thermoacoustic cavity modes have eigenfrequencies closer to the acoustic eigenfrequencies, but this closeness depends on the impact of the flame. In other words, the thermoacoustic cavity modes with a stronger influence of the flame lie farther from the acoustic modes of the acoustic subsystem compared to the ones that are weakly affected by the flame. Figure 2 highlights two pairs of eigenvalues in enclosed boxes - one with eigenfrequencies near 970 Hz (marked as L-mode) and the other near 42 Hz (Helmholtz mode). Each pair comprises eigenvalues from the uncoupled and coupled FOM system. In the pair with frequencies at 970 Hz, the thermoacoustic mode lies close to the passive acoustic mode because the gain of the flame response is very small at such high frequencies (see the FTF gain in Fig. 1) and thus, Fig. 3a shows no discernible difference between the shapes of these modes. On the other hand, Fig. 3b shows that considerable gain of the flame response at lower frequencies strongly affects the Helmholtz mode at 42 Hz and modifies the eigenmode shape (also discussed in [27]).

Apart from the thermoacoustic cavity modes, the coupled FOM contains intrinsic thermoacoustic (ITA) modes, which are completely absent in the modal spectrum of the acoustic subsystem. In the current setup, an ITA mode appears at 111 Hz. For more details about the ITA mode of this setup, the reader is referred to the work of Emmert et al. [27], where the same thermoacoustic setup has been investigated. It is crucial that the thermoacoustic modes are reproducible with sufficient accuracy from the reduced thermoacoustic system. As the three aforementioned ther-

moacoustic modes have different features, we use them as a reference to investigate the suitability of different MOR methods in predicting these modes.

It should also be noted that the acoustic subsystem (uncoupled FOM) is stable as all the eigenvalues have negative growth rate. This is an important condition for applicability of TBR and IRKA, which is discussed in the next section. Model order reduction of an unstable uncoupled FOM is out of scope for this study. Thus, for the rest of the study, the full-order model of the acoustic subsystem (passive system) is considered to be stable, which is generally the case due to damping caused by acoustic losses. Although the size of the studied FOM is small with $N = 78$ degrees of freedom, we can learn important differences among the different MOR methods.

3 MODEL ORDER REDUCTION

Let us consider a linear time-invariant single-input single-output full order model (FOM) in state-space representation as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) &= \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{b}u(t) \\ y(t) &= \mathbf{c}\mathbf{x}(t)\end{aligned}\tag{4}$$

where, $u(t)$ and $y(t)$ are the input and output, respectively. \mathbf{x} , \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{b} and \mathbf{c} have same dimensions as in Eqn. (2). MOR seeks a state-space model with state vector $\mathbf{x}_r(t) \in \mathbb{R}^r$ ($r \ll N$) that features approximately the same dynamics as the FOM. This reduced order model (ROM) is represented as:

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{\mathbf{x}}_r(t) &= \mathbf{A}_r\mathbf{x}_r(t) + \mathbf{b}_ru(t) \\ y(t) &= \mathbf{c}_r\mathbf{x}_r(t)\end{aligned}\tag{5}$$

where $\mathbf{A}_r \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$, $\mathbf{b}_r \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times 1}$, $\mathbf{c}_r \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times r}$. Note that the input $u(t)$ and the output $y(t)$ are identical in the full and reduced models.

The MOR methods considered in this study are based on projections. In projective MOR, the FOM is projected onto a suitable subspace of dimension r such that important dynamics of the original system is retained. First, a basis $\mathbf{V} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times r}$ spanning an r -dimensional subspace is chosen. If this subspace contains the important dynamics of the original system, we can approximate $\mathbf{x}(t) \approx \mathbf{V}\mathbf{x}_r(t)$. Substituting this approximation in the first equation of Eqn. (4),

we get:

$$\mathbf{V}\dot{\mathbf{x}}_r(t) = \mathbf{A} \mathbf{V} \mathbf{x}_r(t) + \mathbf{b} u(t) + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(t) \quad (6)$$

where, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(t)$ is the error introduced due to the approximation. Then, we choose a subspace with basis $\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times r}$ such that $\mathbf{W}^T \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(t) = 0$. Left multiplying Eqn. (6) with \mathbf{W}^T gives the Petrov-Galerkin projection:

$$\mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{V} \dot{\mathbf{x}}_r(t) = \mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{A} \mathbf{V} \mathbf{x}_r(t) + \mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{b} u(t) \quad (7)$$

For more details on projections, the reader is referred to [32]. Eqn. (7) can now be converted to a reduced order equation by left multiplying with $(\mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{V})^{-1}$:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\mathbf{x}}_r(t) &= \mathbf{L} \mathbf{A} \mathbf{V} \mathbf{x}_r(t) + \mathbf{L} \mathbf{b} u(t) \\ y(t) &= \mathbf{c} \mathbf{V} \mathbf{x}_r(t) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where, $\mathbf{L} = (\mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{V})^{-1} \mathbf{W}^T$. Thus, comparing Eqn. (5) with Eqn. (8) gives $\mathbf{A}_r = \mathbf{L} \mathbf{A} \mathbf{V}$, $\mathbf{b}_r = \mathbf{L} \mathbf{b}$ and $\mathbf{c}_r = \mathbf{c} \mathbf{V}$. The selection of basis for \mathbf{V} and \mathbf{W} is what differentiates various projective MOR methods. The MOR methods discussed in this study are modal truncation, truncated balanced realization, and iterative rational Krylov algorithm. We use the *sssMOR* toolbox developed at TU Munich for applying these MOR methods to our application case. Documentation of this toolbox can be found in [33]. We briefly discuss these methods in the following subsections.

3.1 Modal Truncation (MT)

In this method, the state vector \mathbf{x} is transformed to modal coordinates with $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{V}_{\text{MT}} \mathbf{x}_r$, where the columns of \mathbf{V}_{MT} are formed by the r right eigenvectors of \mathbf{A} . The other basis \mathbf{W}_{MT} is formed by the r left eigenvectors of \mathbf{A} . The r right and left eigenvectors are chosen corresponding to r eigenvalues λ with smallest magnitude. There are other possible criteria to select the eigenvalues, for example, λ with largest real part or dominance measure [34]. One can also select eigenvalues and eigenvectors that are close to those of targeted thermoacoustic modes [20, 21]. However, r eigenvalues with smallest magnitude gave consistent result for the application in this study. Thus, the criterion for

selection of λ can be case dependent. Here, we briefly present the procedure mathematically. The matrices \mathbf{V}_{MT} and \mathbf{W}_{MT} are:

$$\mathbf{V}_{\text{MT}} = [\mathbf{t}_1 \dots \mathbf{t}_r]; \quad \mathbf{W}_{\text{MT}}^T = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_1^T \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{I}_r^T \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

where, \mathbf{t}_k and \mathbf{l}_k are the right and left eigenvectors, respectively, for $k = 1, 2, \dots, r$ ($\mathbf{A}\mathbf{t}_k = \lambda_k\mathbf{t}_k$ and $\mathbf{l}_k^T\mathbf{A} = \lambda_k\mathbf{l}_k^T$). Thus, \mathbf{A}_r , \mathbf{b}_r and \mathbf{c}_r can be computed as shown in Eqn. (8). It is evident that this method is same as modal or Galerkin expansion with minor differences in the selection criterion of the eigenvectors.

There are two methods to compute eigenvalues λ and the corresponding left and right eigenvectors - 1) compute only r eigenvalues and eigenvectors iteratively; 2) select r eigenvalues and eigenvectors from the complete eigen-decomposition of \mathbf{A} according to a criterion. The first method is practical for large systems as complete eigen-decomposition requires high computational effort. For small systems, both ways of selecting λ and eigenvectors are equally feasible. In Fig. 4, we show how new eigenvalues are included with increasing order r . As mentioned earlier, λ with smallest magnitudes are selected in this study and thus, the radius of inclusion of λ increases with increasing r .

As discussed briefly in the Introduction, modal truncation provides an option to choose certain modes that are physically relevant to thermoacoustic analysis. However, Antoulas [14] has shown that MT has difficulty in capturing the transfer behavior and gives slow convergence. It should be noted that the coordinates of the reduced system are restricted to the eigenvectors of the matrix \mathbf{A} . This can be disadvantageous if there are other state directions important to the transfer behavior. A more detailed analysis of the ROM from modal truncation is discussed in Section 4.

3.2 Truncated Balanced Realization (TBR)

In order to explain TBR, first the concepts of controllability and observability need to be explained. Controllability provides a relation between the input $u(t)$ and the state vector $\mathbf{x}(t)$. For a system to be completely controllable, it should be possible to steer the system from initial state $\mathbf{x}(t_0) = \mathbf{0}$ to an arbitrary state $\mathbf{x}(t) = \mathbf{x}_e$ with a suitable input $u(t)$ in finite time. The state directions that are easily controllable require less input energy to transfer the system in those state directions. These easily controllable state directions can be determined using the controllability Gramian \mathbf{W}_c

defined as [35]:

$$\mathbf{W}_c = \int_0^{\infty} e^{\mathbf{A}t} \mathbf{b} \mathbf{b}^T e^{\mathbf{A}^T t} dt \quad (10)$$

Observability, on the other hand, provides a relation between the output $y(t)$ and the state $\mathbf{x}(t)$. For a system to be observable, one should be able to determine any state $\mathbf{x}(t)$ from the time-history of output $y(t)$ [36]. The states that are well observable provide most energy to the output for $u(t) = 0$. Similar to the controllability Gramian, the observability Gramian is defined as follows [35]:

$$\mathbf{W}_o = \int_0^{\infty} e^{\mathbf{A}^T t} \mathbf{c}^T \mathbf{c} e^{\mathbf{A}t} dt \quad (11)$$

It should be noted that these Gramians are symmetric and positive semi-definite matrices. Thus, their eigenvalues are real and non-negative. The eigenvectors corresponding to the set of the largest eigenvalues of \mathbf{W}_c and \mathbf{W}_o give the most controllable and observable state directions, respectively.

Now, we want to retain those states that play a dominant role in the input-output relation. Therefore, those states that are both well controllable and observable need to be retained and thus, we need to consider both Gramians (\mathbf{W}_c and \mathbf{W}_o) together. This process is called *balancing*. It should be noted that balancing is possible for a stable FOM (here, acoustic subsystem) only [35]. Algorithm 1 provides a summary of the steps involved in TBR. The first step is to compute the Gramians, which are solution to the Lyapunov equations. Cholesky decomposition of \mathbf{W}_c and \mathbf{W}_o into triangular matrices \mathbf{S} and \mathbf{R} , respectively, and subsequent Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) of $\mathbf{R}^T \mathbf{S}$ can be done for balancing \mathbf{W}_c and \mathbf{W}_o . The truncated matrices of \mathbf{U} and \mathbf{P} are used to build the basis of \mathbf{V}_{TB} and \mathbf{W}_{TB}^T for projective MOR. For more details about TBR, the reader is referred to [14, 35, 36].

Σ contains the decreasing order of the Hankel Singular Values (HSV) from SVD of $\mathbf{R}^T \mathbf{S}$, which represent the energy from input to output for the singular vectors (Fig. 5). From Fig. 5, it can be comprehended that with every increase in the order of the ROM, left and right singular vectors corresponding to the next singular value are included for computing the basis of \mathbf{W}_{TB} and \mathbf{V}_{TB} . It clearly shows that the singular values considered in reduction after $r \approx 25$ are negligible and thus, ROM with $r = 25$ should have sufficient accuracy. With this decreasing order of HSVs, the selection of optimal reduced order can be automated.

TBR has a significant advantage that the stability of the original system is preserved in the ROM. However, the

Algorithm 1 Truncated Balanced Realization

1. Computation of \mathbf{W}_c and \mathbf{W}_o from the Lyapunov equations :

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{A}\mathbf{W}_c + \mathbf{W}_c\mathbf{A}^T + \mathbf{b}\mathbf{b}^T &= 0 \\ \mathbf{A}^T\mathbf{W}_o + \mathbf{W}_o\mathbf{A} + \mathbf{c}^T\mathbf{c} &= 0\end{aligned}$$

2. Cholesky decomposition of $\mathbf{W}_c = \mathbf{S}\mathbf{S}^T$ and $\mathbf{W}_o = \mathbf{R}\mathbf{R}^T$
 3. Singular Value Decomposition of $\mathbf{R}^T\mathbf{S} = \mathbf{U}\mathbf{\Sigma}\mathbf{P}^T$
 4. Truncate SVD based on singular values $\mathbf{R}^T\mathbf{S} = \mathbf{U}\mathbf{\Sigma}\mathbf{P}^T \approx \mathbf{U}_r\mathbf{\Sigma}_r\mathbf{P}_r^T$
 5. Compute the projection matrices $\mathbf{W}_{\text{TB}}^T = \mathbf{\Sigma}_r^{-1/2}\mathbf{U}_r^T\mathbf{R}^T$ and $\mathbf{V}_{\text{TB}} = \mathbf{S}\mathbf{P}_r\mathbf{\Sigma}_r^{-1/2}$
 6. Compute matrices of the ROM as: $\mathbf{A}_r = \mathbf{W}_{\text{TB}}^T\mathbf{A}\mathbf{V}_{\text{TB}}$, $\mathbf{b}_r = \mathbf{W}_{\text{TB}}^T\mathbf{b}$ and $\mathbf{c}_r = \mathbf{c}\mathbf{V}_{\text{TB}}$
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computation of Gramians can be expensive for large systems [14]. Thus, there are methods with approximate solution to Lyapunov equation [37,38] or with empirical Gramians [39].

3.3 Iterative Rational Krylov algorithm (IRKA)

IRKA is a method based on matching the moments of the transfer function of the FOM at certain expansion points. The transfer function of the FOM $G(s)$ and the ROM $G_r(s)$ can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned}G(s) &= \mathbf{c}(s\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A})^{-1}\mathbf{b} \\ G_r(s) &= \mathbf{c}_r(s\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A}_r)^{-1}\mathbf{b}_r\end{aligned}\tag{12}$$

$G(s)$ can be expanded about $s_0 \in \mathbb{C}$ to give ([40]):

$$G(s) = -\sum_{i=0}^{\infty} m_i (s - s_0)^i\tag{13}$$

where, $m_i = -\mathbf{c}(s_0\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A})^{-(i+1)}\mathbf{b}$ is the i -th moment.

As the computation of the moments is generally ill-conditioned, Krylov-based methods provide a way to match moments without explicitly computing them. The Krylov subspace method provides the projection matrices \mathbf{V} and \mathbf{W}

for projective MOR. A simple choice for the subspace spanned by \mathbf{V} and \mathbf{W} around s_0 can be:

$$\begin{aligned}\text{range}(\mathbf{V}) &= K_r((\mathbf{A} - s_0\mathbf{I})^{-1}, (\mathbf{A} - s_0\mathbf{I})^{-1}\mathbf{b}) \\ \text{range}(\mathbf{W}) &= K_r((\mathbf{A} - s_0\mathbf{I})^{-T}, (\mathbf{A} - s_0\mathbf{I})^{-T}\mathbf{c})\end{aligned}\tag{14}$$

where, $K_r(\mathbf{M}, \mathbf{v}) = \text{span}[\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{M}\mathbf{v}, \dots, \mathbf{M}^{r-1}\mathbf{v}]$. Here, $\text{range}(\mathbf{V})$ and $\text{range}(\mathbf{W})$ give *input* and *output Krylov subspace*, respectively. There are multiple strategies for selection of s_0 and the number of moments to be matched. For more details on various approaches with Krylov methods, the reader is referred to Grimme [40].

Moment matching with IRKA involves seeking $G_r(s)$ which is equal to $G(s)$, along with their derivatives, at certain interpolation points (or shifts) $s_k \in \mathbb{C}$ [41], which can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{c} (s_k\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A})^{-1} \mathbf{b} &= \mathbf{c}_r (s_k\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A}_r)^{-1} \mathbf{b}_r \\ \mathbf{c} (s_k\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A})^{-2} \mathbf{b} &= \mathbf{c}_r (s_k\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A}_r)^{-2} \mathbf{b}_r\end{aligned}\tag{15}$$

for $k = 1, 2, \dots, r$. Gugercin et al. [41] proved that provided s_k is not an eigenvalue of \mathbf{A} or \mathbf{A}_r , if $(s_k\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A})^{-1} \mathbf{b} \in \text{range}(\mathbf{V})$ and $(s_k\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A})^{-T} \mathbf{c} \in \text{range}(\mathbf{W})$, then conditions in Eqn. (15) are satisfied. Like TBR, this method is only applicable to a stable FOM. IRKA uses an iterative process to get the expansion points s_k to achieve \mathcal{H}_2 optimal reduction. This iterative process minimizes the error between G and G_r with respect to \mathcal{H}_2 -norm, which is defined as :

$$\|G - G_r\|_{\mathcal{H}_2} = \left(\frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} |G(i\omega) - G_r(i\omega)|^2 d\omega \right)^{1/2}\tag{16}$$

Algorithm 2 summarises the steps of the IRKA algorithm. Here, one has to provide initial expansion points s_k only and these shifts are adapted in every iteration with negative of $\tilde{\lambda}_k$, the eigenvalues of \mathbf{A}_r . For a detailed explanation of this procedure, the reader is referred to Gugercin et al. [41].

Unlike TBR, which requires expensive computation of Gramians, IRKA only requires LU decomposition of $(s_k\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A})$ to build the Krylov subspaces. Thus, it is numerically efficient and suitable for relatively high-dimensional systems. However, the Krylov subspace methods discussed above have a significant disadvantage that the stability of the ROM is not guaranteed. The stability of the ROM depends on the initial shifts for IRKA [41]. Gugercin et al. [41]

Algorithm 2 Iterative Rational Krylov algorithm [41]

- Input** : initial s_k for $k = 1, 2, \dots, r$
 $\mathbf{V}_{\text{Kr}} \leftarrow$ input Krylov subspace around s_k
 $\mathbf{W}_{\text{Kr}} \leftarrow$ output Krylov subspace around s_k
1. while relative change in $s_k >$ tolerance for $k = 1, 2, \dots, r$:
 2. $\mathbf{A}_r = (\mathbf{W}_{\text{Kr}}^T \mathbf{V}_{\text{Kr}})^{-1} \mathbf{W}_{\text{Kr}}^T \mathbf{A} \mathbf{V}_{\text{Kr}}$,
 $\mathbf{b}_r = (\mathbf{W}_{\text{Kr}}^T \mathbf{V}_{\text{Kr}})^{-1} \mathbf{W}_{\text{Kr}}^T \mathbf{b}$, $\mathbf{c}_r = \mathbf{c} \mathbf{V}_{\text{Kr}}$
 3. $s_k \leftarrow -\tilde{\lambda}_k(\mathbf{A}_r)$
 4. Update \mathbf{V}_{Kr} and \mathbf{W}_{Kr}
-

has shown that with initial s_k chosen as the negative of r eigenvalues of \mathbf{A} , IRKA generally provides a stable reduced model. Nevertheless, it must be verified after reduction that the stability is preserved. In the application of IRKA for this study, the initial shifts are chosen as the negative of the r smallest magnitude eigenvalues of \mathbf{A} . As modal truncation also uses r smallest magnitude eigenvalues of \mathbf{A} , the reader can refer to Fig. 4 to find the eigenvalues used for initial shifts for IRKA method with increasing order r . Please note that Fig. 4 only shows the eigenvalues with positive imaginary part, but there exist complex conjugates, which are also used for the initial shifts.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

With the three MOR methods discussed before, we now compare the performance of these methods in two ways:

1) Comparison of relative error in the transfer function of the ROMs; 2) Comparison of thermoacoustic modes of the coupled FOM (explained in Section 2) with the ones reproduced with the coupled ROMs.

4.1 Transfer Function

As explained briefly in the Introduction, it can be important to preserve the transfer behavior of the acoustic subsystem if the feedback from \dot{q}' to u'_{ref} dominates for some thermoacoustic modes. Therefore, we investigate the performance of the three MOR methods in preserving the transfer behavior. Figure 6 shows the normalized error in the transfer function of the ROM (G_r) with order r ranging from 2 to 46. Normalized relative error of the transfer function is defined as follows :

$$\text{relative error} = \frac{\|G(i\omega) - G_r(i\omega)\|_2}{\|G(i\omega)\|_2} \quad (17)$$

where, $G(i\omega)$ and $G_r(i\omega)$ are the transfer functions of FOM and ROM at frequency ω , respectively. Here, frequency ω belongs to a vector of frequencies with logarithmic interval of 0.012 in the range 1 – 5000Hz and $\|\cdot\|_2$ is the 2-norm

of a vector. It is evident that TBR and IRKA perform better than modal truncation for $r > 20$. It is interesting to note that the error for modal truncation saturates to the order $10^{-3} - 10^{-2}$. This observation is corroborated by the conclusions from Antoulas [14] as discussed in Section 3.1.

Figure 7 shows the transfer function of the FOM along with the ROMs from the three methods at $r = 20$. It is clear that modal truncation captures the high-magnitude peaks in the transfer function because these peaks are at the eigenfrequencies of the acoustic subsystem. However, the reduced models from TBR and IRKA are able to capture the transfer behavior over wider frequency ranges. With visible deviation of G_r for modal truncation from the transfer function of the FOM at ITA frequency of 111 Hz (Fig. 7a), one can expect higher error in capturing the ITA mode with modal truncation because the intrinsic modes are primarily caused due to the feedback between \dot{q}' and u'_{ref} , which is here represented with the transfer behavior of the acoustic subsystem. This observation will be discussed in more details in Section 4.2.2.

4.2 Coupling with FTF

After coupling the acoustic ROMs with the FTF, it is important to ascertain whether the eigenmodes of the reduced thermoacoustic models match with the ones of the full thermoacoustic model. Two types of modes - thermoacoustic cavity modes and intrinsic modes - are used for comparing the MOR methods.

4.2.1 Thermoacoustic Cavity Modes:

These modes have oscillation frequencies that lie in general close to the eigenfrequencies of the acoustic model (FOM) as shown in Fig. 2. However, the influence of the flame on the acoustic modes can vary, as exemplified by two eigenmodes at 970 Hz and 42 Hz. As mentioned in Section 2, the mode at 970 Hz is weakly affected by the flame due to negligible gain of the FTF, whereas the mode at 42 Hz is strongly damped along with a significant modification in its shape (Fig. 2, 3). Figure 8 displays the errors in computation of the real and imaginary parts of the eigenvalue corresponding to the cavity mode at 970 Hz for different MOR methods. The relative error in the real part is defined as follows:

$$\text{Rel. error Real part} = \left| \frac{\Re(\lambda_{\text{coupled ROM}} - \lambda_{\text{coupled FOM}})}{\Re(\lambda_{\text{coupled FOM}})} \right| \quad (18)$$

where λ is the respective eigenvalue. The relative error of the imaginary part is defined in an analogous manner. For ROM order $r > 10$, the accuracy of all the methods is high, with relative errors below 10^{-2} for both real and imaginary

parts. It is evident that MT performs exceptionally well at $r < 20$ compared to the other two methods. It is also possible to retrieve the full states from the coupled ROMs to compare the eigenmode shapes using the relation $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{V}\mathbf{x}_r$. For comparison among eigenmodes from different reduced thermoacoustic systems, the eigenmodes are phase-shifted to match the phase of heat release rate and normalized with the value at the downstream end. The eigenvector of this 970 Hz mode is reproduced by all the MOR methods with good accuracy for ROM order $r > 10$ that there is no discernible difference among these methods (mode shape with only magnitude of \hat{u}' with $r = 12$ shown in Fig. 9). This demonstrates that all the methods are suitable to capture thermoacoustic cavity modes that are weakly affected by the flame.

On the contrary, modal truncation fails to accurately represent the mode at 42 Hz. Figure 10 shows that with modal truncation the error in eigenvalue saturates at about 10^{-2} and 10^{-3} for the real and imaginary parts, respectively, whereas the error continues to decrease for TBR and IRKA. From the acoustic velocity mode shape \hat{u}' in Fig. 11a, it can be seen that the mode shape from MT does not correspond well with the mode shape of the full model. In the inset of Fig. 11a, even at $r = 36$, the mode shape from modal truncation has large deviations from the mode shape of the coupled FOM. On the other hand, the mode shapes from TBR and IRKA have better accuracy and improve significantly with increasing order, see Figs. 11b and 11c. The deviation in the mode shape from MT at the discontinuity caused by the flame is due to Gibbs' phenomenon, as reported by Sayadi et al. [23]. The oscillations associated to Gibbs' phenomenon near the flame discontinuity can be critical for thermoacoustic analysis, because they can affect the velocity u'_{ref} at the reference point, which is generally located near the flame. The mode shapes from TBR and IRKA do not exhibit such deviations at sufficiently high order. Although the comparison is shown here using the magnitude of \hat{u}' , the comparison using the phase of \hat{u}' is similar (not shown here).

4.2.2 ITA mode:

Intrinsic thermoacoustic (ITA) modes are of special interest for the present study. ITA modes have been found repeatedly to be the dominant unstable thermoacoustic modes. Their shapes as well as frequencies may differ significantly from those of acoustic eigenmodes [26–31]. Obviously, MOR techniques suitable for thermoacoustic applications should provide thermoacoustic ROMs that accurately capture cavity as well as ITA modes.

Figure 12 shows that the error in the eigenvalue of the ITA mode does not decrease for modal truncation after $r = 25$ (error in the real part saturates at the order of 10^{-1}), whereas it decreases for TBR and IRKA. Like the cavity modes, the eigenmode shape of the ITA mode can also be compared. Figure 13a shows that the reduced thermoacoustic system derived from modal truncation also suffers from Gibbs phenomenon for this mode. On the contrary, the mode shapes are more accurate for TBR and IRKA, which further improves with increasing order (Fig. 13b,13c).

Modal truncation uses the eigenmodes of the FOM based on the selection of eigenvalues to construct the ROM, thus restricting to only the state directions corresponding to these eigenmodes. However, ITA mode is an eigenmode of the coupled system lying far from the passive acoustic eigenmodes and the state directions required to capture ITA modes are not used by the modal truncation method. As the feedback between \dot{q}' and u'_{ref} plays the dominant role intrinsic modes, it is essential to retain those states which are crucial for the transfer behavior of the acoustic subsystem. Therefore, to reproduce ITA modes accurately in the reduced system, reduction methods based on preserving the transfer behavior yield better results.

Summary of results:

From the comparison of the ROMs coupled with an FTF, it can be concluded that the eigenmodes of the full thermoacoustic system lying far from the eigenmodes of the acoustic subsystem are not captured accurately with modal truncation. This is demonstrated with two examples - one with the Helmholtz mode at 42 Hz that significantly differs from the passive acoustic mode due to strong influence of the flame; the other with the ITA mode that is absent in the modal basis of the acoustic subsystem. Both of these modes require larger modal basis with modal truncation in order to be captured with modest accuracy. At such high order of the ROM, the purpose of model order reduction would effectively be lost. Contrarily, truncated balanced realization and iterative rational Krylov algorithm are able to accurately reproduce the thermoacoustic cavity modes (irrespective of the influence of the flame) and the intrinsic thermoacoustic modes.

5 CONCLUSION

In a hybrid thermoacoustic setup, the acoustic and the flame models are separate subsystems. These subsystems can be coupled with each other to build a full thermoacoustic system. MOR of the acoustic subsystem can drastically reduce the computational cost for repeated computations required for robust stability analysis of large domains. This study demonstrates the application of three MOR methods to the acoustic subsystem and discusses their suitability. After reduction, the ROMs are coupled with an FTF to reproduce the modes of the full system. It is demonstrated that the reduced thermoacoustic system from modal truncation is unable to accurately capture ITA modes, and those thermoacoustic cavity modes that are strongly influenced by the flame, because these eigenmodes lie far from the passive acoustic eigenmodes. On the contrary, truncated balanced realization and IRKA, which are based on preserving the transfer behavior, result in reduced systems capable of accurately reproducing all the thermoacoustic modes. Thus, for model order reduction of the acoustic subsystem in hybrid setups, preserving the transfer behavior is essential to replicate all the thermoacoustic modes in the reduced system with sufficient accuracy.

With the knowledge gained from this study, application of MOR methods to higher-order 3D systems (with order of $10^5 - 10^6$ degrees of freedom) or systems with more informed physics, like LNSE, can be envisaged in the future. Three-dimensional systems from Helmholtz equation might feature 3D modes and systems derived from LNSE may exhibit hydrodynamic modes. In such cases, these features should also be considered when applying MOR. With larger systems, it can be expected that the MOR techniques discussed in the presented form become computationally expensive. Thus, more efficient algorithms based on the principles of the methods discussed here would have to be applied to gain computational advantage.

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Fig. 1: Hybrid thermoacoustic setup with coupling of the acoustic subsystem and FTF through u'_{ref} and q' . Note: This figure is not up to scale.

Fig. 2: Eigenvalues of the coupled (*) and uncoupled (□) FOM. Three sets of eigenvalues are highlighted for analysis in Section 4 - an ITA mode at 111 Hz, and two thermoacoustic cavity modes: 42 Hz (Helmholtz mode) and 970 Hz (L-mode).

(a) 970 Hz

(b) 42 Hz

Fig. 3: Acoustic velocity mode shape for cavity mode with the coupled and uncoupled FOM at (a) 970 Hz and (b) 42 Hz. The vertical dashed black line depicts the location of the flame. Location x is the axial coordinate of the combustor in Fig. 1.

Fig. 4: Eigenvalues added to ROM with increasing order r (only positive $\Im(\lambda)$ shown). Circle of inclusion of eigenvalues with $r = 12$ (—), $r = 24$ (—) and $r = 36$ (—). $\Re(\lambda)$ and $\Im(\lambda)$ correspond to growth rate and eigenfrequency, respectively.

Fig. 5: Hankel Singular Values with increasing order r for the acoustic subsystem.

Fig. 6: Relative error in transfer function based on Eqn. (17) with increasing order of the ROM for the three reduction methods. Order of FOM $N = 78$.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 7: Transfer function of FOM and ROMs from the three reduction methods at $r = 20$. Vertical line at 111 Hz is to depict the ITA frequency.

Fig. 8: Error in the real (top) and imaginary (bottom) part of the eigenvalue of the thermoacoustic cavity mode at 970 Hz with increasing order of ROM (r). Relative error is defined by Eqn. (18).

Fig. 9: Magnitude of \hat{u}' for the cavity mode at 970 Hz from the coupled ROMs from MT, TBR and IRKA with $r = 12$. Mode shape for the coupled FOM has been shown for reference. The vertical dashed lines in black and magenta show the flame location and the location of u'_{ref} , respectively.

Fig. 10: Error in the real (top) and imaginary (bottom) part of the eigenvalue of the thermoacoustic cavity mode at 42 Hz (Helmholtz mode) with increasing order of ROM (r). Relative error is defined by Eqn. (18).

(a) MT

(b) TBR

(c) IRKA

Fig. 11: Magnitude of \hat{u}' for the cavity mode at 42 Hz (Helmholtz mode) from the coupled ROMs derived with respective MOR method. The mode shape for the coupled FOM has also been shown for reference. Insets show magnification for the region $x = 0.32m$ to $x = 0.4m$. The vertical dashed lines in black and magenta show the flame location and the location of u'_{ref} , respectively.

Fig. 12: Error in the real (top) and imaginary (bottom) part of the eigenvalue of the ITA mode with increasing order of ROM (r). Relative error is defined by Eqn. (18).

(a) MT

(b) TBR

(c) IRKA

Fig. 13: Magnitude of \hat{u}' for the ITA mode at 111 Hz from the coupled ROMs derived with respective MOR method. The mode shape for the coupled FOM has also been shown for reference. Insets show magnification for the region $x = 0.32m$ to $x = 0.4m$. The vertical dashed lines in black and magenta show the flame location and the location of u'_{ref} , respectively.